

Parasite	Host	Link	Month	Year	Observer	District	Latitude	Longitude	
Asian Koel	Common Myna	https://ebird.org/checklist/S58807181		8	2019	Md Zaber Ansary	Dhaka	23.81	90.41
Asian Koel	Common Myna	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S71949984		7	2020	Mayank Namdeo	Sonitpur	26.67	92.86
Asian Koel	House Crow	https://ebird.org/checklist/S36638055		10	1990	Prasad JN	Bangalore	12.97	77.65
Asian Koel	House Crow	https://ebird.org/checklist/S48182171		8	2018	Ashwin Viswanathan	Bangalore	12.97	77.65
Asian Koel	House Crow	https://ebird.org/checklist/S47738504		8	2018	Jay Govind	Bangalore	12.97	77.65
Asian Koel	House Crow	https://ebird.org/checklist/S48101885		8	2018	Prasad JN	Bangalore	12.97	77.65
Asian Koel	House Crow	https://ebird.org/checklist/S38652748		8	2017	rima dhillon	Chandigarh	30.73	76.78
Asian Koel	House Crow	https://ebird.org/checklist/S41003415		11	2017	NALINI RAMAN	Chennai	13.06	80.25
Asian Koel	House Crow	https://ebird.org/checklist/S47344427		7	2018	Sreekumar Chirukandoth	Chennai	13.06	80.25
Asian Koel	House Crow	https://ebird.org/checklist/S48712759		9	2018	Sreekumar Chirukandoth	Chennai	13.06	80.25
Asian Koel	House Crow	https://ebird.org/checklist/S50388775		12	2018	Subramanian Sankar	Chennai	13.06	80.25
Asian Koel	House Crow	https://ebird.org/checklist/S59816617		8	2019	Sreekumar Chirukandoth	Chennai	13.06	80.25
Asian Koel	House Crow	https://ebird.org/checklist/S25066423		9	2015	Sharang Satish	Coimbatore	10.97	76.92
Asian Koel	House Crow	https://ebird.org/checklist/S61620157		11	2014	Santharam V	Dindigul	10.47	77.84
Asian Koel	House Crow	https://ebird.org/checklist/S24742801		8	2015	Rajesh Kalra	East Delhi	28.63	77.3
Asian Koel	House Crow	https://ebird.org/checklist/S47702911		8	2018	Polly Kalamassery	Ernakulam	9.98	76.29
Asian Koel	House Crow	https://ebird.org/checklist/S49208546		10	2018	Panchapakesan Jeganathan	Erode	11.52	77.47
Asian Koel	House Crow	https://ebird.org/checklist/S39378981		9	2017	Dinesh Singal	Gautam Buddha Nagar	28.34	77.6
Asian Koel	House Crow	https://ebird.org/checklist/S60276706		10	2019	Rajesh Kalra	Gautam Buddha Nagar	28.34	77.6
Asian Koel	House Crow	https://ebird.org/checklist/S66657225		8	2017	Celesta von Chamier	Islamabad	33.72	73.04
Asian Koel	House Crow	https://ebird.org/checklist/S59634401		9	2019	Wouter Plomp	Islamabad	33.72	73.04
Asian Koel	House Crow	https://ebird.org/checklist/S39969625		10	2017	Lakshmikanth Neve	Jalgaon	21.01	75.56
Asian Koel	House Crow	https://ebird.org/checklist/S48074845		8	2018	Shilpa Gadgil	Jalgaon	21.01	75.56
Asian Koel	House Crow	https://ebird.org/checklist/S37843646		6	2017	Jitendra Sarmah	Kamrup	26.32	91.6
Asian Koel	House Crow	https://ebird.org/checklist/S32958134		12	2016	Hopeland P	Kancheepuram	12.88	79.87
Asian Koel	House Crow	https://ebird.org/checklist/S39347816		9	2017	Sreekumar Chirukandoth	Kancheepuram	12.88	79.87
Asian Koel	House Crow	https://ebird.org/checklist/S49394225		10	2018	Sheeja Rajagopal	Kancheepuram	12.88	79.87
Asian Koel	House Crow	https://ebird.org/checklist/S20378689		6	1996	Dr. Dilip K G	Kannur	11.87	75.37
Asian Koel	House Crow	https://ebird.org/checklist/S25404422		10	2015	sasidharan manekkara	Kannur	11.87	75.37
Asian Koel	House Crow	https://ebird.org/checklist/S66262402		3	2020	Shyamkumar Puravankara	Kasaragod	12.5	74.99
Asian Koel	House Crow	https://ebird.org/checklist/S70898443		6	2020	sameer mhetras	Kolhapur	16.71	74.24
Asian Koel	House Crow	https://ebird.org/checklist/S37484023		6	2017	Lekshmi Jayakumar	Kottayam	9.59	76.52
Asian Koel	House Crow	https://ebird.org/checklist/S52485845		2	2019	Sreedevi A	Kottayam	9.59	76.52
Asian Koel	House Crow	https://ebird.org/checklist/S49007467		9	2018	Duncan Orr-Ewing	Madhyamanchal	27.47	85.27
Asian Koel	House Crow	https://ebird.org/checklist/S66905386		7	2019	Sandesh Thapa	Madhyamanchal	27.47	85.27
Asian Koel	House Crow	https://ebird.org/checklist/S59172640		8	2019	John Jesudasan	Mumbai	19.02	72.85
Asian Koel	House Crow	https://ebird.org/checklist/S70619525		6	2020	Sameer Ashar	Mumbai Suburban	19.15	72.88
Asian Koel	House Crow	https://ebird.org/checklist/S25386604		10	2015	Vijaya Lakshmi	Mysore	12.3	76.63
Asian Koel	House Crow	https://ebird.org/checklist/S39948450		10	2017	Vijaya Lakshmi	Mysore	12.3	76.63
Asian Koel	House Crow	https://ebird.org/checklist/S42326024		1	2018	Vijaya Lakshmi	Mysore	12.3	76.63
Asian Koel	House Crow	https://ebird.org/checklist/S57280751		6	2019	Soumya Kundu	North 24 Parganas	22.62	88.4
Asian Koel	House Crow	https://ebird.org/checklist/S41763858		1	2018	Dattaram Phadte	North Goa	15.52	73.98
Asian Koel	House Crow	https://ebird.org/checklist/S60415215		10	2019	Ayush Rajotia	North West Delhi	28.72	77.07
Asian Koel	House Crow	https://ebird.org/checklist/S40297267		11	2017	Surendhar Boobalan	Puducherry	11.94	79.81
Asian Koel	House Crow	https://ebird.org/checklist/S60933465		10	2019	Surendhar Boobalan	Puducherry	11.94	79.81
Asian Koel	House Crow	https://ebird.org/checklist/S20867186		8	2014	Rajneesh Suvarna	Pune	18.52	73.86
Asian Koel	House Crow	https://ebird.org/checklist/S31221224		8	2016	Abhijeet Avate	Pune	18.52	73.86
Asian Koel	House Crow	https://ebird.org/checklist/S38009857		7	2017	Chirag Munje	Pune	18.52	73.86
Asian Koel	House Crow	https://ebird.org/checklist/S39612913		10	2017	Chirag Munje	Pune	18.52	73.86
Asian Koel	House Crow	https://ebird.org/checklist/S47743376		8	2018	Swapnil Thatte	Pune	18.52	73.86

Parasite	Host	Link	Month	Year	Observer	District	Latitude	Longitude	
Asian Koel	Common Myna	https://ebird.org/checklist/S58807181		8	2019	Md Zaber Ansary	Dhaka	23.81	90.41
Asian Koel	House Crow	https://ebird.org/checklist/S62627311		12	2019	Siddharth Biniwale	Pune	18.52	73.86
Asian Koel	House Crow	https://ebird.org/checklist/S71543322		7	2020	Swapnil Thatte	Pune	18.52	73.86
Asian Koel	House Crow	https://ebird.org/checklist/S48513869		9	2018	Elavarasan M	Salem	11.66	78.15
Asian Koel	House Crow	https://ebird.org/checklist/S47683802		8	2001	Sharad Apte	Sangli	16.85	74.58
Asian Koel	House Crow	https://ebird.org/checklist/S47962701		7	2004	Sharad Apte	Sangli	16.85	74.58
Asian Koel	House Crow	https://ebird.org/checklist/S47962859		8	2004	Sharad Apte	Sangli	16.85	74.58
Asian Koel	House Crow	https://ebird.org/checklist/S47289112		9	2008	Sharad Apte	Sangli	16.85	74.58
Asian Koel	House Crow	https://ebird.org/checklist/S34415089		10	2008	Sharad Apte	Sangli	16.85	74.58
Asian Koel	House Crow	https://ebird.org/checklist/S31917830		8	2016	Sharad Apte	Sangli	16.85	74.58
Asian Koel	House Crow	https://ebird.org/checklist/S38616693		7	2017	Sharad Apte	Sangli	16.85	74.58
Asian Koel	House Crow	https://ebird.org/checklist/S40335671		8	2017	Sharad Apte	Sangli	16.85	74.58
Asian Koel	House Crow	https://ebird.org/checklist/S47797618		8	2018	Sharad Apte	Sangli	16.85	74.58
Asian Koel	House Crow	https://ebird.org/checklist/S70898599		6	2020	Sharad Apte	Sangli	16.85	74.58
Asian Koel	House Crow	https://ebird.org/checklist/S31671987		9	2016	Yogesh Parashar	South Delhi	28.48	77.19
Asian Koel	House Crow	https://ebird.org/checklist/S59300420		8	2019	Gillian Wright	South Delhi	28.48	77.19
Asian Koel	House Crow	https://ebird.org/checklist/S39399563		9	2017	David Clark	Southern Province	6.24	80.54
Asian Koel	House Crow	https://ebird.org/checklist/S25563573		10	2015	Kaustubh Rau	Sri Potti Sriramulu Nellore	14.26	79.92
Asian Koel	House Crow	https://www.facebook.com/groups/711328729034093/permalink/746031448897154/		6	2016	Abhay Hule	Thane	19.45	73.37
Asian Koel	House Crow	https://ebird.org/checklist/S31986562		9	2016	sheeba nanjan	Tiruppur	10.9	77.38
Asian Koel	House Crow	https://ebird.org/checklist/S38687515		8	2017	Panchapakesan Jeganathan	Tiruppur	10.9	77.38
Asian Koel	House Crow	https://ebird.org/checklist/S39156621		9	2017	Panchapakesan Jeganathan	Tiruppur	10.9	77.38
Asian Koel	House Crow	https://ebird.org/checklist/S40127060		10	2017	Panchapakesan Jeganathan	Tiruppur	10.9	77.38
Asian Koel	House Crow	https://ebird.org/checklist/S40311514		11	2017	Panchapakesan Jeganathan	Tiruppur	10.9	77.38
Asian Koel	House Crow	https://ebird.org/checklist/S40938927		12	2017	Panchapakesan Jeganathan	Tiruppur	10.9	77.38
Asian Koel	House Crow	https://ebird.org/checklist/S50167209		11	2018	Panchapakesan Jeganathan	Tiruppur	10.9	77.38
Asian Koel	House Crow	https://ebird.org/checklist/S38155122		7	2017	vrinda lath	Udupi	13.54	74.87
Drongo Cuckoo	Indian White-eye	https://ebird.org/checklist/S59502287		6	2019	Shahed Raiyan	Sylhet	24.9	91.87
Asian Koel	Large-billed Crow	https://ebird.org/checklist/S32079600		10	2016	Sivakumar Swaminathan	Ahmadabad	23.02	72.57
Asian Koel	Large-billed Crow	https://ebird.org/checklist/S37848600		6	2017	Rajesh Kalra	Solan	31.05	76.92
Asian Koel	Large-billed Crow	https://ebird.org/checklist/S49642193		11	2018	David Clark	Southern Province	6.24	80.54
Asian Koel	Red-vented Bulbul	https://ebird.org/checklist/S59658558		9	2019	Wouter Plomp	Islamabad	33.72	73.04
Asian Koel	Red-vented Bulbul	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S71863980		7	2020	Jaydev Mandal	Kamrup	26.32	91.6
Banded Bay Cuckoo	Black-headed Cuckooshrike	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S48645601		9	2018	Yashwant Shekhawat	Umaria	23.6	81.08
Banded Bay Cuckoo	Black-headed Cuckooshrike	https://ebird.org/checklist/S31889641		4	2010	Craig Robson	Uva Palata	6.84	81.34
Banded Bay Cuckoo	Common Iora	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S41700879		1	2018	Prashantha Krishna M C	Dakshina Kannada	12.84	75.25
Banded Bay Cuckoo	Common Iora	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S40044060		10	2017	Hemanth Byatroy	Dharwad	15.46	75.01
Banded Bay Cuckoo	Common Iora	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S44441134		10	2017	Skanda S N	Dharwad	15.46	75.01
Banded Bay Cuckoo	Common Iora	Birds of Kerala-Status & Distribution				K.V.Eldhose	Ernakulam	9.98	76.29
Banded Bay Cuckoo	Common Iora	https://www.biodiversitylibrary.org/item/188616#page/122/mode/1up		5		M.C.A. Jackson	Idukki	9.92	77.1
Banded Bay Cuckoo	Common Iora	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S39993920		10	2017	Yousaf Olavilam	Kannur	11.87	75.37
Banded Bay Cuckoo	Common Iora	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S41007270		12	2017	Bijumon K E	Kannur	11.87	75.37
Banded Bay Cuckoo	Common Iora	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S61036914		10	2019	Lathika K K	Kannur	11.87	75.37
Banded Bay Cuckoo	Common Iora	https://ebird.org/checklist/S61166991		11	2019	Mohan Choron	Kannur	11.87	75.37
Banded Bay Cuckoo	Common Iora	https://besgroup.org/2010/11/18/banded-bay-cuckoo-chick-and-common-iora-in-india/		11	2010	Abhijeet Avate	Kolhapur	16.71	74.24
Banded Bay Cuckoo	Common Iora	https://ebird.org/checklist/S64705553		2	2020	Narendra Latthe	Kolhapur	16.71	74.24
Banded Bay Cuckoo	Common Iora	https://ebird.org/checklist/S48054568		11	2012	Chinmay Rahane	North Goa	15.52	73.98
Banded Bay Cuckoo	Common Iora	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S37681150		6	2011	S Prasanth Narayanan	Palakkad	10.79	76.65
Banded Bay Cuckoo	Common Iora	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S37443591		7	2016	Abhijeet Rasal	Pune	18.52	73.86
Banded Bay Cuckoo	Common Iora	https://www.facebook.com/groups/306780776062327/?post_id=2215776941829358		9	2013	Shardul Kelkar	Ratnagiri	16.99	73.31

Parasite	Host	Link	Month	Year	Observer	District	Latitude	Longitude	
Asian Koel	Common Myna	https://ebird.org/checklist/S58807181		8	2019	Mid Zaber Ansary	Dhaka	23.81	90.41
Banded Bay Cuckoo	Common Iora	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S20934109		12	2014	Mandar Bhagat	South Goa	15.11	74.12
Banded Bay Cuckoo	Common Iora	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S20804754		12	2014	Mandar Bhagat	South Goa	15.11	74.12
Banded Bay Cuckoo	Common Iora	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S32163823		10	2016	Mandar Bhagat	South Goa	15.11	74.12
Banded Bay Cuckoo	Common Iora	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S40392330		11	2017	Mandar Bhagat	South Goa	15.11	74.12
Banded Bay Cuckoo	Common Iora	https://www.biodiversitylibrary.org/item/189533#page/431/mode/1up		10		Heinz Lainer	South Goa	15.11	74.12
Banded Bay Cuckoo	Common Iora	http://www.orientalbirdimages.org/search.php?Bird_ID=441&Bird_Image_ID=53821		9	2011	Subharghya Das	The Nilgiris	11.49	76.73
Banded Bay Cuckoo	Common Iora	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S41634880		1	2018	Ashwin Viswanathan	The Nilgiris	11.49	76.73
Banded Bay Cuckoo	Common Iora	https://stage.sriranga.digital/mns/php/bookreader/templates/book.php?volume=017-018&part=01-04&pagenum=0001&vtype=blb#page/10/mode/1up		9		V Santharam	Thrissur	10.53	76.21
Banded Bay Cuckoo	Common Iora	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S40085568		10	2017	Vrinda Lath	Udupi	13.54	74.87
Banded Bay Cuckoo	Common Iora	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S48123206		8	2018	Vrinda Lath	Udupi	13.54	74.87
Banded Bay Cuckoo	Common Iora	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S54162910		10	2011	Bijoy Venugopal	Uttara Kannada	14.79	74.69
Banded Bay Cuckoo	Common Iora	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S25840541		11	2015	Mohit Aggarwal	Uttara Kannada	14.79	74.69
Banded Bay Cuckoo	Common Iora	https://www.biodiversitylibrary.org/item/95250#page/1006/mode/1up				James Davidson	Uttara Kannada	14.79	74.69
Banded Bay Cuckoo	Common Iora	https://www.biodiversitylibrary.org/item/95250#page/1006/mode/1up				T R Bell	Uttara Kannada	14.79	74.69
Banded Bay Cuckoo	Common Iora	https://m.facebook.com/groups/5448197410?view=permalink&id=10152239307297411		8	2014	Sharan Venkatesh	Virudhunagar	9.57	77.96
Banded Bay Cuckoo	Common Iora	Birds of Kerala-Status & Distribution		9	1990	P.K.Uthaman	Wayanad	11.69	76.13
Banded Bay Cuckoo	Common Iora	Birds of Kerala-Status & Distribution		9	1994	K.G. Raghu	Wayanad	11.69	76.13
Banded Bay Cuckoo	Common Woodshrike	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S64560018		2	2020	Rajesh Radhakrishnan	Palakkad	10.79	76.65
Banded Bay Cuckoo	Orange Minivet	https://ebird.org/checklist/S52637091		1	2008	Todd Pepper	Uva Palata	6.84	81.34
Banded Bay Cuckoo	Red-whiskered Bulbul	https://www.biodiversitylibrary.org/item/188616#page/122/mode/1up		4		M.C.A. Jackson	Idukki	9.92	77.1
Banded Bay Cuckoo	Small Minivet	Birds of Kerala-Status & Distribution		12	1998	Praveen J	Palakkad	10.79	76.65
Common Cuckoo	Long-tailed shrike	https://www.facebook.com/photo.php?fbid=871708912915681		7	2015	Raja Aamir	Anantnag	33.73	75.15
Common Cuckoo	Long-tailed shrike	https://www.facebook.com/photo?fbid=10217357374949227		7	2020	Ali Akhter Gani	Anantnag	33.73	75.15
Common Cuckoo	Long-tailed Shrike	https://www.facebook.com/groups/5448197410/permalink/10156641843872411/		8	2019	Abhai Mishra	Dehradun	30.32	78.03
Common Cuckoo	Long-tailed Shrike	https://www.sanctuarynaturefoundation.org/photography/photo-feature/going-cuckoo		8	2016	Kishan Meena	Jaipur	26.91	75.79
Common Cuckoo	Long-tailed Shrike	https://www.facebook.com/groups/524156214416700/permalink/1521809544651357/		9	2017	Sudhir Garg	Jaipur	26.91	75.79
Common Cuckoo	Long-tailed Shrike	https://www.facebook.com/groups/5448197410/permalink/10155831487687411/		9	2018	Anil Mahajan	Jalgaon	21.01	75.56
Common Cuckoo	Long-tailed Shrike	https://www.facebook.com/groups/5448197410/permalink/10151878850637411/		8	2013	Raj Rawal	Lahul and Spiti	32.62	77.38
Common Cuckoo	Long-tailed Shrike	https://www.facebook.com/groups/5448197410/permalink/1015577507507411/		8	2018	Shiv Kumar	Lahul and Spiti	32.62	77.38
Common Cuckoo	Long-tailed Shrike	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S59725581		8	2019	Prashant Negi	Lahul and Spiti	32.62	77.38
Common Cuckoo	Olive-backed Pipit	https://ebird.org/checklist/S59921662		7	2015	Puja Sharma	Uttarkashi	30.93	78.48
Common Cuckoo	Red-billed Leiothrix	https://m.facebook.com/photo.php?fbid=887832184626699&id=100001997775468&set=gm.10153092495107411		8	2015	Sidhu Chettri	Darjeeling	26.93	88.36
Common Cuckoo	Red-billed Leiothrix	https://ebird.org/checklist/S71862337		7	2020	Kynsai Ria	East Khasi	25.37	91.75
Common Hawk Cuckoo	Jungle Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S36445115		4	2017	Jaya Rakesh Kannan	Balaghat	21.86	80.37
Common Hawk Cuckoo	Jungle Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S59843018		9	2019	Sangita Mani	Balaghat	21.86	80.37
Common Hawk Cuckoo	Jungle Babbler	https://www.facebook.com/story.php?story_fbid=1999703383496385&id=100003702282289		7	2020	Sovan Gupta	Bankura	23.16	87.06
Common Hawk Cuckoo	Jungle Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S56212643		5	2019	Prakash G	Coimbatore	10.97	76.92
Common Hawk Cuckoo	Jungle Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S56178109		5	2019	Praveen Shankar Balasubramanian	Coimbatore	10.97	76.92
Common Hawk Cuckoo	Jungle Babbler	http://www.bnhsenvis.nic.in/writereaddata/buceros_11.pdf		7	1886	James Davidson	Dhule	21.06	74.69
Common Hawk Cuckoo	Jungle Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S63751275		1	2020	Robert Tizard	Ernakulam	9.98	76.29
Common Hawk Cuckoo	Jungle Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S25375268		10	2015	Yogesh Parashar	Faridabad	28.31	77.33
Common Hawk Cuckoo	Jungle Babbler	https://www.facebook.com/photo.php?fbid=619840051365955				Dhaval Vargiya	Gaya	24.72	84.86
Common Hawk Cuckoo	Jungle Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S48734601		9	2016	Rajiv R	Gurgaon	28.36	76.87
Common Hawk Cuckoo	Jungle Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S49226324		10	2018	Siddharth Biniwale	Hoshangabad	22.75	77.73
Common Hawk Cuckoo	Jungle Babbler	https://www.facebook.com/photo?fbid=2356344157710391&set=gm.10156110619127411		12	2018	Anshuman Sahasrabhojane	Idukki	9.92	77.1
Common Hawk Cuckoo	Jungle Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S21794159		2	2015	Lekshmi Jayakumar	Kottayam	9.59	76.52
Common Hawk Cuckoo	Jungle Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S37203367		5	2017	Rushil Fernandes	Lucknow	26.84	80.95
Common Hawk Cuckoo	Jungle Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S21221709		3	1999	Arun Bhaskaran	Malappuram	11.05	76.07
Common Hawk Cuckoo	Jungle Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S38045881		7	2017	Rajesh Radhakrishnan	Palakkad	10.79	76.65

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Asian Koel	Common Myna	https://ebird.org/checklist/S58807181		8	2019	Mid Zaber Ansary	Dhaka	23.81 90.41
Common Hawk Cuckoo	Jungle Babbler	https://www.sanctuarynaturefoundation.org/photography/photo-feature/going-cuckoo		1	2014	L J Mendis Wikremesinghe	Puttalam	8.04 79.83
Common Hawk Cuckoo	Jungle Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S65769569		12	2018	Debankur Biswas	South 24 Parganas	22.14 88.4
Common Hawk Cuckoo	Jungle Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S50921808		9	2015	Amit Bandekar	South Goa	15.11 74.12
Common Hawk Cuckoo	Jungle Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S25260849		10	2015	Raman Kumar	South West Delhi	28.59 77.03
Common Hawk Cuckoo	Jungle Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S29988770		5	2016	Steffin Babu	South West Delhi	28.59 77.03
Common Hawk Cuckoo	Jungle Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S28155960		3	2016	Praveen J	Thrissur	10.53 76.21
Common Hawk Cuckoo	Jungle Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S48339315		8	2018	Praveen es	Thrissur	10.53 76.21
Common Hawk Cuckoo	Jungle Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S48122960		8	2018	Sreekumar E R	Thrissur	10.53 76.21
Common Hawk Cuckoo	Jungle Babbler	https://www.facebook.com/adarsh.damodar.3/posts/2462805580493111		8	2019	Adarsh Damodar	Thrissur	10.53 76.21
Common Hawk Cuckoo	Jungle Babbler	https://stage.sriranga.digital/mms/php/bookreader/templates/book.php?volume=017-018&part=01-04&pagenum=0001&vtype=blb/page/10/mode/1up		1		V Santharam	Thrissur	10.53 76.21
Common Hawk Cuckoo	Jungle Babbler	https://stage.sriranga.digital/mms/php/bookreader/templates/book.php?volume=017-018&part=01-04&pagenum=0001&vtype=blb/page/10/mode/1up		8		V Santharam	Thrissur	10.53 76.21
Common Hawk Cuckoo	Jungle Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S24840188		1	2013	Ramit Singal	Udupi	13.54 74.87
Common Hawk Cuckoo	Jungle Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S3177616		9	2016	Ramit Singal	Udupi	13.54 74.87
Common Hawk Cuckoo	Jungle Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S31928976		10	2016	Vrinda Lath	Udupi	13.54 74.87
Common Hawk Cuckoo	Jungle Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S31713781		9	2016	Aparajita Datta	Uttara Kannada	14.79 74.69
Common Hawk Cuckoo	Jungle Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S31761108		9	2016	Devathi Parashuram	Uttara Kannada	14.79 74.69
Common Hawk Cuckoo	Large Grey Babbler	https://www.facebook.com/818089491578671/photos/basw.AboMKnXGDELLyRWr1gQ1_pFk1Kor050fMmMNI_WOmG4svgwz7B3BHDQxZ856bftSjswWA08uxUjaGmuOquVXqck7b6zbn8vlyz5AuwQnwgCFw32Mw3RPEj					Bengaluru Rural	13.28 77.61
Common Hawk Cuckoo	Large Grey Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S25027696		9	2015	Hemanth Byatroy	Dharwad	15.46 75.01
Common Hawk Cuckoo	Large Grey Babbler	https://www.facebook.com/kannadaPrabhaOnline/photos/basw.AboMOA1wYgONtk2oRzfTrtK5jQuuPIEMrN_tLbAbL6fy28azo-WFYCR8WdeAYcC3TS8frjdu8o5KYVsecbsP67Uj0ALv				Kushal Adaki	Dharwad	15.46 75.01
Common Hawk Cuckoo	Large Grey Babbler	https://www.facebook.com/groups/nikenhike/?post_id=2102847893099728		10	2018	Chirag Paikar	Gandhinagar	23.22 72.64
Common Hawk Cuckoo	Large Grey Babbler	https://www.facebook.com/ritul.sathwara/posts/1129034513924360		10	2018	Ritul Sathwara	Gandhinagar	23.22 72.64
Common Hawk Cuckoo	Large Grey Babbler	https://www.facebook.com/groups/indianbirds/?post_id=10153178627977411		11	2015	Venugopal Bsnl	Hyderabad	17.39 78.49
Common Hawk Cuckoo	Large Grey Babbler	https://www.facebook.com/photo?fbid=10157610628149395		10	2019	Syamala Rupakula	Hyderabad	17.39 78.49
Common Hawk Cuckoo	Large Grey Babbler	https://www.facebook.com/groups/indianbirds/?post_id=10151010594322411		9	2012	Sudhir Garg	Jaipur	26.91 75.79
Common Hawk Cuckoo	Large Grey Babbler	http://orientalbirdimages.org/search.php?Bird_ID=435&Bird_Image_ID=110056		10	2015	Arijit Banerjee	Jaipur	26.91 75.79
Common Hawk Cuckoo	Large Grey Babbler	https://www.facebook.com/groups/5448197410/permalink/10154078966827411/		10	2016	Sachin Khattar	Jaipur	26.91 75.79
Common Hawk Cuckoo	Large Grey Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S49007042		10	2018	Yogesh Parashar	Jaipur	26.91 75.79
Common Hawk Cuckoo	Large Grey Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S19610456		8	2014	Anil Mahajan	Jalgaon	21.01 75.56
Common Hawk Cuckoo	Large Grey Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S39804237		10	2017	Anil Mahajan	Jalgaon	21.01 75.56
Common Hawk Cuckoo	Large Grey Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S50013635		11	2018	Anil Mahajan	Jalgaon	21.01 75.56
Common Hawk Cuckoo	Large Grey Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S60664428		10	2019	Kaustubh Machnurkar	Kolhapur	16.71 74.24
Common Hawk Cuckoo	Large Grey Babbler	https://thebutterflydiaries.wordpress.com/2009/10/21/the-forcibly-adopted-child/		10	2009	Ashwin Baidur	Pune	18.52 73.86
Common Hawk Cuckoo	Large Grey Babbler	https://m.facebook.com/groups/129188390523855?view=permalink&id=747147008727987&_rdr		9	2015	Arun Varghese	Pune	18.52 73.86
Common Hawk Cuckoo	Large Grey Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S38956713		9	2017	Chirag Munje	Pune	18.52 73.86
Common Hawk Cuckoo	Large Grey Babbler	https://ebird.org/checklist/S39383173		9	2017	Sneha Gupta	Pune	18.52 73.86
Common Hawk Cuckoo	Large Grey Babbler	https://www.facebook.com/groups/punebirds/?post_id=2405039502872265		7	2018	Omkar Sumant	Pune	18.52 73.86
Common Hawk Cuckoo	Large Grey Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S49264155		10	2018	Adil Ali	Pune	18.52 73.86
Common Hawk Cuckoo	Large Grey Babbler	https://m.facebook.com/groups/5448197410?view=permalink&id=10157574846622411		9	2018	Raju Karia	Rajkot	22.3 70.8
Common Hawk Cuckoo	Large Grey Babbler	https://www.facebook.com/story.php?story_fbid=2586032071459659&id=100001586732320		8	2019	Raju Karia	Rajkot	22.3 70.8
Common Hawk Cuckoo	Large Grey Babbler	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=XtwHdIQ8YhY		10	2014	Dharmendra Khandal	Sawai Madhopur	26.01 76.36
Common Hawk Cuckoo	Large Grey Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S25637109		1	2015	Parikshit Khisty	Tumkur	13.37 76.64
Common Hawk Cuckoo	Large Grey Babbler	https://www.facebook.com/groups/sanctuaryasia/?post_id=10156841227971103		10	2018	Tushar Tripathi T T		
Common Hawk Cuckoo	Large Grey Babbler	https://www.instagram.com/p/CBSQrNvgR-v/?igshid=17zsnheff5dzw				Prakit Bhatt		
Common Hawk Cuckoo	Yellow-billed Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S24836569		8	2015	Rishov Biswas	Bangalore	12.97 77.65
Common Hawk Cuckoo	Yellow-billed Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S38968818		9	2017	Albin Jacob	Bangalore	12.97 77.65
Common Hawk Cuckoo	Yellow-billed Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S62982495		1	2020	Rahul Singh	Bangalore	12.97 77.65
Common Hawk Cuckoo	Yellow-billed Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S31163783		8	2016	Madhurima Das	Chamrajnagar	11.93 76.94
Common Hawk Cuckoo	Yellow-billed Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S27576469		2	2016	Susy Varughese	Chennai	13.06 80.25
Common Hawk Cuckoo	Yellow-billed Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S62518516		12	2019	Santharam V	Chittoor	13.48 78.83

Parasite	Host	Link	Month	Year	Observer	District	Latitude	Longitude
Asian Koel	Common Myna	https://ebird.org/checklist/558807181		8	2019	Mid Zaber Ansary	Dhaka	23.81 90.41
Common Hawk Cuckoo	Yellow-billed Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/530914773		7	2016	sasidharan manekkara	Kannur	11.87 75.37
Common Hawk Cuckoo	Yellow-billed Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/531635782		9	2016	sasidharan manekkara	Kannur	11.87 75.37
Common Hawk Cuckoo	Yellow-billed Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/566152803		3	2020	Jaya Rakesh Kannan	Madurai	9.93 78.12
Common Hawk Cuckoo	Yellow-billed Babbler	https://ebird.org/checklist/538950077		9	2017	Vijaya Lakshmi	Mysore	12.3 76.63
Common Hawk Cuckoo	Yellow-billed Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/564692835		2	2020	Shwetha Bharathi	Mysore	12.3 76.63
Common Hawk Cuckoo	Yellow-billed Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/569807591		5	2020	Puja Deb	Nagappattinam	10.77 79.84
Common Hawk Cuckoo	Yellow-billed Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/547087349		7	2018	Preethy Prasanth	Palakkad	10.79 76.65
Common Hawk Cuckoo	Yellow-billed Babbler	https://ebird.org/checklist/526108328		11	2018	Praveen E S	Palakkad	10.79 76.65
Common Hawk Cuckoo	Yellow-billed Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/519798061		7	2014	Jessica Luis	Puducherry	11.94 79.81
Common Hawk Cuckoo	Yellow-billed Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/565553989		2	2020	Vigneshwaran B	Puducherry	11.94 79.81
Common Hawk Cuckoo	Yellow-billed Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/551727924		1	2019	Periyasamy Rajangam	Salem	11.66 78.15
Common Hawk Cuckoo	Yellow-billed Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/532186691		10	2016	Raja Simma Pandiyan	Thanjavur	10.66 79.25
Common Hawk Cuckoo	Yellow-billed Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/543583253		3	2018	Duraiswamy Navaneetham	Thanjavur	10.66 79.25
Common Hawk Cuckoo	Yellow-billed Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/521527233		2	2013	Alan Knue	The Nilgiris	11.49 76.73
Common Hawk Cuckoo	Yellow-billed Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/532252333		10	2016	Raja Simma Pandiyan	Thiruvurur	10.77 79.63
Common Hawk Cuckoo	Yellow-billed Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/552427376		2	2019	Raja Simma Pandiyan	Thiruvurur	10.77 79.63
Common Hawk Cuckoo	Yellow-billed Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/523555617		5	2015	Abhirami C	Thirissur	10.53 76.21
Common Hawk Cuckoo	Yellow-billed Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/529321101		4	2016	Chandrasekaran Venkatraman	Virudunagar	9.42 77.84
Common Hawk Cuckoo	Yellow-billed Babbler	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=00UMcCAkgec				Sreekumar Mahe		
Drongo Cuckoo	Black-chinned Babbler	https://m.facebook.com/story/graphql_permalink?graphql_id=UzpFStEWMDAwMIMzNiExMjYwNpW5zoxNTEzMTc4OTAYMTU0MTQ0		9	2019	Trilok Singh Bisht	Nainital	29.28 79.47
Drongo Cuckoo	Dark-fronted Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/549284473		10	2018	Omkar Dharwadkar	North Goa	15.52 73.98
Drongo Cuckoo	Dark-fronted Babbler	https://www.facebook.com/photo/?fbid=391216864585428				Isuru Dayananda	Puttalam	8.04 79.83
Drongo Cuckoo	Tawny-bellied Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/560579798		10	2019	Arun Venkataramanan	Pune	18.52 73.86
Drongo Cuckoo	Tawny-bellied Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/560734813		10	2019	Avinash Sharma	Pune	18.52 73.86
Drongo Cuckoo	Yellow-eyed Babbler	https://www.facebook.com/media/set/?set=a.10150336267801262.343486.504511261&type=3		10	2011	Surendra Agnihotri	Nagpur	21.15 79.09
Emerald Cuckoo	Purple Sunbird	https://www.facebook.com/groups/sanctuaryasia/?post_id=10157342987981103		5	2019	Himanka B Deka	Kamrup	26.32 91.6
Grey-bellied Cuckoo	Ashy Prinia	https://www.sanctuarynaturefoundation.org/photography/photo-feature/going-cuckoo		9	2012	Nagesh Vannur	Kolhapur	16.71 74.24
Grey-bellied Cuckoo	Ashy Prinia	http://www.orientalbirdimages.org/search.php?Bird_ID=440&Bird_Image_ID=177258		10	2019	Praveen Joshi	Yavatmal	20.39 78.13
Grey-bellied Cuckoo	Black-headed Cuckooshrike	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/525991745		11	2015	Omkar Dharwadkar	North Goa	15.52 73.98
Grey-bellied Cuckoo	Common Tailorbird	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/562579779		12	2019	Raghupathy Kannan	Coimbatore	10.97 76.92
Grey-bellied Cuckoo	Common Tailorbird	https://archive.org/details/NLBW23/page/n65/mode/2up		10	1982	Taej Mundkur	Pune	18.52 73.86
Grey-bellied Cuckoo	Common Tailorbird	https://www.sanctuarynaturefoundation.org/photography/photo-feature/going-cuckoo		9	2012	Nitin Jain	Pune	18.52 73.86
Grey-bellied Cuckoo	Common Tailorbird	https://www.facebook.com/groups/indianbirds/?post_id=10153188872347411		11	2015	Rohit Kolhatkar	Pune	18.52 73.86
Grey-bellied Cuckoo	Common Tailorbird	http://www.orientalbirdimages.org/search.php?Bird_ID=440&Bird_Image_ID=53815		8	2011	Abhijith A V	Wayanad	11.69 76.13
Grey-bellied Cuckoo	Common Tailorbird	https://www.facebook.com/groups/129188390523855/permalink/2291751447600861/		11	2019	Shobha Chandrasekharan	Wayanad	11.69 76.13
Grey-bellied Cuckoo	House Sparrow	https://m.facebook.com/story/graphql_permalink?graphql_id=UzpFStEWMDAwMTI2NjE4NzIxMDpW5zoxMDElNTk0MjI4MzE5MjQxMQ%3D%3D		10	2018	Manas Gupta	Pune	18.52 73.86
Grey-bellied Cuckoo	Plain Prinia	https://www.facebook.com/groups/indianbirds/?post_id=10155954593097411		11	2018	Kishan Meena	Jaipur	26.91 75.79
Grey-bellied Cuckoo	Plain Prinia	https://www.facebook.com/groups/5448197410/permalink/10152953678422411/		10	2014	Sanjay Nafdey	Nagpur	21.15 79.09
Grey-bellied Cuckoo	Purple-rumped Sunbird	https://www.facebook.com/groups/indianbirds/?post_id=10150351436002411		11	2011	Sawan Deshmukh	Amravati	20.93 77.75
Grey-bellied Cuckoo	Purple-rumped Sunbird	https://www.facebook.com/photo/?fbid=2807593889325725		12	2017	Suyog Bhore	Nashik	20 73.79
Grey-bellied Cuckoo	Purple-rumped Sunbird	https://www.facebook.com/groups/5448197410/permalink/10155916382407411/		10	2018	Vivek Naik	Pune	18.52 73.86
Grey-bellied Cuckoo	Purple-rumped Sunbird	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/561664174		11	2019	Sharad Apte	Sangli	16.85 74.58
Grey-bellied Cuckoo	Purple-rumped Sunbird	https://www.sanctuarynaturefoundation.org/photography/photo-feature/going-cuckoo		10	2009	Aniruddha Dikshit	Satara	17.68 74.02
Grey-bellied Cuckoo	Purple-rumped Sunbird	https://www.facebook.com/groups/indianbirds/?post_id=10155887346467411		10	2018	Vinay Gote	Solapur	17.66 75.91
Grey-bellied Cuckoo	Purple-rumped Sunbird	https://www.facebook.com/groups/indianbirds/?post_id=10156769843582411		9	2019	Santoshbhu Dhakpade	Solapur	17.66 75.91
Grey-bellied Cuckoo	Purple-rumped Sunbird	https://www.facebook.com/photo/?fbid=1990604227749831&set=gm.10158374316016103				Akbar Shaikh	Solapur	17.66 75.91
Grey-bellied Cuckoo	Purple-rumped Sunbird	https://www.facebook.com/groups/5448197410/permalink/10154988650832411/		10	2017	Abhishek Sonkusare	Yavatmal	20.39 78.13
Grey-bellied Cuckoo	Zitting Cisticola	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/539596703		10	2017	Sahana M	Mysore	12.3 76.63
Grey-bellied Cuckoo	Zitting Cisticola	https://www.facebook.com/charaachar/posts/336184343678609		10	2018	Charaachar	Pune	18.52 73.86

Parasite	Host	Link	Month	Year	Observer	District	Latitude	Longitude
Asian Koel	Common Myna	https://ebird.org/checklist/S58807181		8	2019	Mid Zaber Ansary	Dhaka	23.81 90.41
Himalayan Cuckoo	Grey-headed Canary Flycatcher	https://m.facebook.com/story/graphql_permalink/?graphql_id=Uzn5TE1NzExNjc3NTI6Vks6MTAxNTMzMzY2NDIOMTE%3D		6	2016	Avadhesh Malik	Binsar	29.71 79.76
Indian Cuckoo	Black Drongo	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S32722613		5	1988	Prasad J N	Chamrajnagar	11.93 76.94
Indian Cuckoo	Black Drongo	https://vimeo.com/5844369		6	2009	Uma K	Chamrajnagar	11.93 76.94
Indian Cuckoo	Black Drongo	https://www.facebook.com/photo.php?fbid=4688426797896796		7	2020	Kartik Sundar	East Singhbhum	22.49 86.5
Indian Cuckoo	Black Drongo	https://ebird.org/checklist/S54110370		7	2018	Hemant Kumar	Kathua	32.39 75.52
Indian Cuckoo	Black Drongo	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S46294451		6	2018	Souvik Das	Nadia	23.47 88.56
Indian Cuckoo	Black Drongo	https://m.facebook.com/groups/275478312602273?view=permalink&id=1645565295593561		7	2020	Oken Sanasam	Thoubal	24.64 94
Indian Cuckoo	Black-hooded Oriole	https://www.facebook.com/jetwingnaturalists/posts/1379432692258054		2	2020	Chaminda Jayasekara	Matale	7.47 80.62
Large Hawk Cuckoo	Chestnut-crowned Laughing Thrush	https://ebird.org/checklist/S68906013		9	2017	Puja Sharma	Tehri Garhwal	30.3 78.57
Lesser Cuckoo	Grey-hooded Warbler	https://www.facebook.com/story.php?story_fbid=10207081253569783&id=1234318755		6	2016	Balakrishnan Valappil	Tehri Garhwal	30.3 78.57
Pied Cuckoo	Jungle Babbler	https://www.facebook.com/photo/?fbid=605764622819535&set=gm.10151706411287411		11	2013	Manoj Bind	Amravati	20.93 77.75
Pied Cuckoo	Jungle Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S67162038		10	2014	Neenad Abhang	Amravati	20.93 77.75
Pied Cuckoo	Jungle Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S37998729		10	2005	S Prasanth Narayanan	Bharatpur	27.06 77.29
Pied Cuckoo	Jungle Babbler	https://www.facebook.com/photo/?fbid=10210262511834149&set=gm.10155929301282411		10	2018	Hitesh Chawla	Bharatpur	27.06 77.29
Pied Cuckoo	Jungle Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S61256079		11	2019	Martin Heffron	Bharatpur	27.06 77.29
Pied Cuckoo	Jungle Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S60708351		10	2019	Manjot Singh	Chandigarh	30.73 76.78
Pied Cuckoo	Jungle Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S25653046		10	2015	Monica Kaushik	Dehradun	30.32 78.03
Pied Cuckoo	Jungle Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S39168759		9	2017	AJAY SHARMA	Dehradun	30.32 78.03
Pied Cuckoo	Jungle Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S41299623		12	2017	Pallavi Joshi	Dehradun	30.32 78.03
Pied Cuckoo	Jungle Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S59592785		9	2019	Dhananjai Mohan	Dehradun	30.32 78.03
Pied Cuckoo	Jungle Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S60930914		10	2019	Yogesh Vardev	Faridabad	28.31 77.33
Pied Cuckoo	Jungle Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S59632973		9	2019	Naushad Theba	Gandhinagar	23.22 72.64
Pied Cuckoo	Jungle Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S60072044		9	2019	Irshad Theba	Gandhinagar	23.22 72.64
Pied Cuckoo	Jungle Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S48734601		9	2016	Rajiv R	Gurgaon	28.36 76.87
Pied Cuckoo	Jungle Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S49336393		10	2018	Kavi Nanda	Gurgaon	28.36 76.87
Pied Cuckoo	Jungle Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S31715595		9	2016	Harsha Jayaramaiah	Hoshangabad	22.75 77.73
Pied Cuckoo	Jungle Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S49154623		9	2018	Payal Mehta	Hoshangabad	22.75 77.73
Pied Cuckoo	Jungle Babbler	https://ebird.org/checklist/S38728904		8	2017	Ellen van Kalmthout	Islamabad	33.72 73.04
Pied Cuckoo	Jungle Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S48079720		8	2018	Anil Mahajan	Jalgaon	21.01 75.56
Pied Cuckoo	Jungle Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S61137383		10	2019	Ajay Kumar	Jammu	32.73 74.86
Pied Cuckoo	Jungle Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S25341122		10	2015	Nelson George	Lucknow	26.84 80.95
Pied Cuckoo	Jungle Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S32308749		10	2016	Able Lawrence	Lucknow	26.84 80.95
Pied Cuckoo	Jungle Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S20388778		7	1999	Aashesh Pittie	Medak	18.05 78.26
Pied Cuckoo	Jungle Babbler	https://www.facebook.com/dharm.khandal/posts/10152765957464649		8	2015	Dharmendra Khandal	Sawai Madhopur	26.01 76.36
Pied Cuckoo	Jungle Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S31926758		10	2016	Taksh Sangwan	South West Delhi	28.59 77.03
Pied Cuckoo	Jungle Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S61300091		11	2019	Dipak Gudhekar	Wardha	20.8 78.57
Pied Cuckoo	Large Grey Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S46690624		6	2018	Bhavi K	Coimbatore	10.97 76.92
Pied Cuckoo	Rufous Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S32275879		10	2016	Vridha Lath	Udupi	13.54 74.87
Pied Cuckoo	Streaked Laughingthrush	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S50242756		10	1973	Tony Gaston	Kullu	31.96 77.12
Pied Cuckoo	Streaked Laughingthrush	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S19464037		11	2003	Mike Prince	Nainital	29.28 79.47
Pied Cuckoo	Yellow-billed Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S24533789		9	2014	Raju Kasambe	Bagalkot	16.14 75.62
Pied Cuckoo	Yellow-billed Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S39892738		10	2017	Vinod Shankar	Bangalore	12.97 77.65
Pied Cuckoo	Yellow-billed Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S41712508		1	2018	Sharang Satish	Coimbatore	10.97 76.92
Pied Cuckoo	Yellow-billed Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S49876988		11	2018	Sharang Satish	Coimbatore	10.97 76.92
Pied Cuckoo	Yellow-billed Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S61620157		11	2014	Santharam V	Dindigul	10.47 77.84
Pied Cuckoo	Yellow-billed Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S62692325		12	2019	Jithesh Nochad	Dindigul	10.47 77.84
Pied Cuckoo	Yellow-billed Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S70710816		12	2005	sasidharan manekkara	Kannur	11.87 75.37
Pied Cuckoo	Yellow-billed Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S67885195		5	2003	Deapesh M	Mysore	12.3 76.63
Pied Cuckoo	Yellow-billed Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S69126850		8	2013	Girija T	Mysore	12.3 76.63

Parasite	Host	Link	Month	Year	Observer	District	Latitude	Longitude
Asian Koel	Common Myna	https://ebird.org/checklist/S58807181		8	2019	Mid Zaber Ansary	Dhaka	23.81 90.41
Pied Cuckoo	Yellow-billed Babbler	https://ebird.org/checklist/S24921998		9	2015	Vijaya Lakshmi	Mysore	12.3 76.63
Pied Cuckoo	Yellow-billed Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S24909220		9	2015	Ganeshwar SV	Mysore	12.3 76.63
Pied Cuckoo	Yellow-billed Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S25363137		10	2015	Vijaya Lakshmi	Mysore	12.3 76.63
Pied Cuckoo	Yellow-billed Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S30740394		7	2016	Shwetha Bharathi	Mysore	12.3 76.63
Pied Cuckoo	Yellow-billed Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S31779339		9	2016	Vijaya Lakshmi	Mysore	12.3 76.63
Pied Cuckoo	Yellow-billed Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S42608721		2	2018	Sahana M	Mysore	12.3 76.63
Pied Cuckoo	Yellow-billed Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S58483781		7	2019	Sahana M	Mysore	12.3 76.63
Pied Cuckoo	Yellow-billed Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S59020768		8	2019	Shivaprakash Adavanne	Mysore	12.3 76.63
Pied Cuckoo	Yellow-billed Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S61060388		10	2019	Sahana M	Mysore	12.3 76.63
Pied Cuckoo	Yellow-billed Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S70589897		6	2020	Sahana M	Mysore	12.3 76.63
Pied Cuckoo	Yellow-billed Babbler	https://ebird.org/checklist/S70591408		6	2020	Sahana M	Mysore	12.3 76.63
Pied Cuckoo	Yellow-billed Babbler	https://ebird.org/checklist/S70336884		6	2020	Sahana M	Mysore	12.3 76.63
Pied Cuckoo	Yellow-billed Babbler	https://ebird.org/checklist/S9172000		4	1975	Werner Nezdal	North Western Province	
Pied Cuckoo	Yellow-billed Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S66269065		3	2020	Vigneshwaran B	Puducherry	11.94 79.81
Pied Cuckoo	Yellow-billed Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S66557404		4	2020	Vigneshwaran B	Puducherry	11.94 79.81
Pied Cuckoo	Yellow-billed Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S44772504		8	2017	Hareesha AS	Ramanagara	22.47 70.06
Pied Cuckoo	Yellow-billed Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S20424152		11	1982	Aasheesh Pittie	Rangareddy	17.39 77.84
Pied Cuckoo	Yellow-billed Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S24634123		10	2010	Dr. JR Rajasingh	Salem	11.66 78.15
Pied Cuckoo	Yellow-billed Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S61514760		11	2019	Mohammed Rinaz M	The Nilgiris	11.49 76.73
Pied Cuckoo	Yellow-billed Babbler	https://www.facebook.com/photo/?fbid=10207527897853002&set=gm.10153355046407411		2	2016	Jasmin Sajna	Tirunelveli	8.72 77.47
Pied Cuckoo	Yellow-billed Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S27789253		2	2016	Shanmugam Kalidass	Tiruppur	10.9 77.38
Pied Cuckoo	Yellow-billed Babbler	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S31591255		9	2016	Shanmugam Kalidass	Tiruppur	10.9 77.38
Pied Cuckoo	Yellow-billed Babbler	https://ebird.org/checklist/S69803686		5	2020	Chandula Suriyapperuma	Western Province	
Plaintive Cuckoo	Black-throated Prinia	https://www.facebook.com/photo/?fbid=10206409122444496&set=gm.603277603148406		7	2015	Duhita McNally	Darjeeling	26.93 88.36
Plaintive Cuckoo	Black-throated Prinia	https://www.facebook.com/photo/?fbid=2942151832527611&set=gm.3449707795056749		7	2019	Bapyndap Ryndem	East Khasi	25.37 91.75
Plaintive Cuckoo	Common Tailorbird	https://www.facebook.com/groups/camarena.in/?post_id=2094438924207215		5	2018	Anjan Biswas	North 24 Parganas	22.62 88.4
Plaintive Cuckoo	Common Tailorbird	https://www.facebook.com/groups/bongphotography/?post_id=1084625765048480		8	2018	Madhusudan Sarkar	North 24 Parganas	22.62 88.4
Plaintive Cuckoo	Common Tailorbird	https://www.facebook.com/groups/camarena.in/?post_id=2094016407582800				Antu Halder	North 24 Parganas	22.62 88.4
Plaintive Cuckoo	Common Tailorbird	https://www.facebook.com/groups/sundaywatch.org/?post_id=618192518323581		8	2015	Manobrata Das	South 24 Parganas	22.14 88.4
Plaintive Cuckoo	Plain Prinia	https://www.facebook.com/groups/2403154788/?post_id=10157954091869789		10	2019	Ali Kawser Dany	Dhaka	23.81 90.41
Violet Cuckoo	Olive-backed Sunbird	https://www.facebook.com/gururaj_moorching/posts/10155687808479132		3	2018	Gururaj Moorching	South Andaman	11.74 92.66
Yellow-rumped Honeyguide	Green-backed Tit	https://ebird.org/checklist/S46734405		6	2018	Vivek Rawat	Rudraprayag	
Indian Cuckoo	Black Drongo	https://www.biodiversitylibrary.org/item/183343#page/259/mode/1up		5	1936	H T Storrs	Jalpaiguri	26.68 88.77
Indian Cuckoo	Black Drongo	https://www.biodiversitylibrary.org/item/186193#page/828/mode/1up		5	1951	K K Neelakantan	Palakkad	10.79 76.65
Indian Cuckoo	Black Drongo	http://indianbirds.in/pdfs/IB_12_2_3_NahidETAL_Cuckoos.pdf		4	2011	Mominul Islam Nahid	Dhaka	23.81 90.41
Indian Cuckoo	Black Drongo	http://indianbirds.in/pdfs/IB_12_2_3_NahidETAL_Cuckoos.pdf		6	2011	Mominul Islam Nahid	Dhaka	23.81 90.41
Grey-bellied Cuckoo	Common Tailorbird	Birds of Kerala-Status & Distribution		9	1989	P.K.Uthaman	Wayanad	11.69 76.13
Grey-bellied Cuckoo	Common Tailorbird	Birds of Kerala-Status & Distribution		6	1998	P.K.Uthaman	Wayanad	11.69 76.13
Indian Cuckoo	Black Drongo	Birds of Kerala-Status & Distribution		6	2007	P O Nameer	Thrissur	10.53 76.21
Common Cuckoo	Long-tailed Shrike	https://drive.google.com/file/d/0B3FjoiNii3LpNmI0ZQzYzUtmMuzNi00YjdhLTg2ZDktZThYWESMTewYwFk/view		9	2003	Atul Damankar	Chandrapur	20.21 79.56
Grey-bellied Cuckoo	Ashy Prinia	https://www.biodiversitylibrary.org/item/95250#page/1016/mode/1up				R K Burnett	Hyderabad	17.39 78.49
Grey-bellied Cuckoo	Plain Prinia	https://www.biodiversitylibrary.org/item/95250#page/455/mode/1up				Miss Cockburn	The Nilgiris	11.49 76.73
Grey-bellied Cuckoo	Common Tailorbird	https://www.biodiversitylibrary.org/item/95250#page/456/mode/1up				T R Bell	Uttara Kannada	14.79 74.69
Grey-bellied Cuckoo	Plain Prinia	https://ebird.org/checklist/S49485415		10	2018	Rahul Singh	Bangalore	12.97 77.65
Common Cuckoo	Red-billed Leiothrix	https://www.facebook.com/photo/?fbid=10153262036043082		10	2010	Prabin Pradhan	Darjeeling	26.93 88.36
Emerald Cuckoo	Crimson Sunbird	https://www.facebook.com/groups/177802072394609/?post_id=1652243338283801		8	2020	Luku Ranjan Nath	Kamrup	26.32 91.6
Common Hawk Cuckoo	Yellow-billed Babbler	https://ebird.org/checklist/S72529759		8	2020	Rabinandan Govvarjanam	Bangalore	12.97 77.65
Asian Koel	Common Myna	https://ebird.org/india/checklist/S72760874		8	2020	KARTHIKEYAN R	Madurai	9.93 78.12